

From Traditional Fisheries to a Marine Growth Pole: The Historical Formation of a Marine Economic Hub in Southeast Vietnam (2007–2025)

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Abstract

This article examines the structural transformation of the marine economy in Southeast Vietnam between 2007 and 2025, tracing its evolution from a traditional fisheries-based foundation to an integrated marine economic hub anchored in deep-sea ports, heavy industry, and logistics. Employing a historical political economy approach that combines quantitative analysis (time-series data on GRDP, sectoral composition, and trade flows) with qualitative assessment (policy frameworks and institutional drivers), the study identifies three major phases of transformation: (1) 2007–2012, characterized by the activation of a port–industrial structure through large-scale infrastructure investment; (2) 2013–2019, marked by expansion and deeper integration into trans-Pacific and EU trade networks, alongside rapid growth in logistics services and foreign direct investment (FDI); and (3) 2020–2025, during which the region faced significant disruptions from COVID-19 but underwent restructuring toward green marine economy and energy transition. The findings indicate that the region’s growth model exhibits three defining features: a developmental state playing a strategic infrastructure-building role; strong dependence on global trade flows; and relatively limited domestic value-added in key sectors. The article critically assesses whether Southeast Vietnam has emerged as a genuine “growth pole” in the Perrouxian sense or functions primarily as a strategic node within East Asian supply chains. It further discusses long-term sustainability challenges amid geopolitical volatility and global decarbonization pressures.

Keywords: *Industrial logistics, Global trade, Maritime growth, Port development.*

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Introduction

During the first two decades of the twenty-first century, the coastal region of Southeast Vietnam underwent a profound structural transformation: from an economy primarily based on fisheries and resource extraction to a highly integrated port–industrial–logistics complex. At the global level, the ocean economy has increasingly been recognized as a major growth driver of the twenty-first century, closely associated with trade expansion, global supply chains, and port-centered urbanization (OECD, 2016; UNCTAD, 2019, 2023). Within this broader context, Vietnam institutionalized its marine development strategy through Resolution No. 09-NQ/TW (The Central Committee of the Communist Party of Vietnam, 2007) and further elevated its ambitions in Resolution No. 36-NQ/TW (The Central Committee of the Communist Party of Vietnam, 2018), setting the objective of transforming the marine economy into a long-term pillar of national growth.

Prior to 2007, however, the economic structure of Southeast Vietnam’s coastal zone remained strongly shaped by small-scale fisheries and traditional resource-based activities. Coastal fishing communities faced mounting pressures related to resource depletion and livelihood insecurity (Armitage & Marschke,

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2013; FAO, 2014). Statistical evidence confirms the significant contribution of fisheries to the provincial economy during the 1990–2000 period (Ba Ria–Vung Tau Statistical Office, 2002). Nevertheless, the expansion of coastal industrialization and the rapid development of industrial zones laid the institutional and infrastructural foundations for a new growth cycle (Ba Ria–Vung Tau Management Board of Industrial Zones, 2013, 2018, 2020).

A decisive turning point was the strategic planning of Vietnam’s seaport system and the Southeast Seaport Cluster (Group 5) (Ministry of Transport, 2013, 2017), which facilitated the emergence of deep-sea port complexes integrated into regional logistics networks. According to port regionalization theory, port development triggers the spatial restructuring of hinterland economies and deeper supply-chain integration (Notteboom & Rodrigue, 2005; Rodrigue, 2020). At the urban scale, maritime ports continue to play a central role in shaping industrial–urban configurations (Hall & Jacobs, 2012). In this context, Southeast Vietnam represents a paradigmatic case of maritime-led growth, in which port infrastructure, industrial clustering, and global trade are mutually reinforcing (Stopford, 2009; Grammenos, 2010).

This article analyzes the historical formation of Southeast Vietnam’s marine economic hub between 2007 and 2025 as a long-term structural transformation—from traditional fisheries to a “marine growth pole” anchored in deep-sea ports, foreign direct investment (FDI), and logistics. By integrating provincial statistical data (Ba Ria–Vung Tau Statistical Office, 2016, 2021; Ba Ria–Vung Tau Provincial People’s Committee, 2020) with contemporary ocean economy frameworks (OECD, 2016; UNCTAD, 2023), the study addresses a central question: Has Southeast Vietnam evolved into an endogenous marine growth pole in its own right, or does it function primarily as a strategic node within global and East Asian trade networks?

Literature Review

Research on the development of Southeast Vietnam’s marine economy lies at the intersection of three major strands of scholarship: (i) national marine strategy and maritime economic development; (ii) port planning and coastal industrialization; and (iii) empirical data and regional historical transformation.

At the strategic level, Resolution No. 09-NQ/TW first established the marine economy as a national development pillar (The Central Committee of the Communist Party of Vietnam, 2007), while Resolution No. 36-NQ/TW reframed it within a sustainability-oriented and integrated development paradigm (The Central Committee of the Communist Party of Vietnam, 2018). These policy shifts align with global narratives that position the ocean economy as a key driver of twenty-first-century growth (OECD, 2016). International institutions such as the World Bank (2019) and the Asian Development Bank (2022) similarly emphasize connectivity, infrastructure integration, and coastal industrial upgrading as central to Vietnam’s long-term competitiveness.

Vietnamese scholarship has approached the marine strategy from both economic and political perspectives. Linh (2010) and De (2008) argue that the marine strategy reflects not only economic modernization but also geopolitical repositioning amid global integration. Thom (2015), adopting a political economy approach, highlights the state’s strategic leadership in maritime economic development during 1996–2010, laying the institutional foundation for the acceleration phase after 2007. At the macro level, global assessments of fisheries and marine sustainability (FAO, 2014, 2022) provide essential context for understanding the structural limits of small-scale fisheries and the pressures that encouraged economic diversification in coastal Vietnam.

Regarding infrastructure and port development, the Master Plan for the Development of Vietnam’s Seaport System (Ministry of Transport, 2013) and Decision No. 3655/QĐ-BGTVT approving the detailed plan for the Southeast Seaport Cluster (Ministry of Transport, 2017) positioned the Cai Mep–Thi Vai complex as a southern international gateway. From a theoretical standpoint, port regionalization explains how port expansion restructures hinterland economic spaces and integrates supply chains (Notteboom & Rodrigue, 2005; Rodrigue, 2020). Maritime logistics literature further demonstrates the

strategic interdependence between ports, industrial clusters, and global shipping networks (Stopford, 2009; Song & Panayides, 2012; Grammenos, 2010). At the urban level, ports remain central nodes in industrial–urban configurations (Hall & Jacobs, 2012). UNCTAD’s Review of Maritime Transport (2019, 2023) reinforces this perspective by documenting the growing concentration of global trade flows in major port clusters.

Empirical and regional sources provide critical evidence for reconstructing structural change. Provincial statistical data for 1991–2001 and 2002–2015 (Ba Ria–Vung Tau Statistical Office, 2002, 2016), along with the 2020 Statistical Yearbook (Ba Ria–Vung Tau Statistical Office, 2021), indicate a steady decline in agriculture and fisheries and a rise in industrial and port-related services. Comparative data from Ho Chi Minh City (Hochiminh City Statistical Office, 1996, 2017, 2021) situate Southeast Vietnam within the Southern Key Economic Region. Reports from the Ba Ria–Vung Tau Management Board of Industrial Zones (2013, 2018, 2020) and the Ho Chi Minh City Industrial Parks and Export Processing Zones Management Board (2011) document the pivotal role of FDI and heavy industry in shaping coastal growth clusters. The provincial logistics development plan (Transportation Department of Ba Ria–Vung Tau Province, 2011) further reveals early institutional preparation for logistics expansion.

Historical and regional studies deepen the analysis. Hiep and Sang (2017) and Hiep and Tram (2020) explore the long-term management and exploitation of the Southeast marine space, while Quang (2019) provides comparative insights from Southwest Vietnam. Notably, Lai’s doctoral dissertation (Lai, 2022) offers a systematic examination of socio-economic restructuring and spatial transformation in Southeast Vietnam during 2007–2020, providing an empirical and analytical foundation for extending the discussion toward marine economic integration and port–industrial restructuring.

Despite substantial scholarship on marine strategy and port planning, existing studies remain fragmented. Few analyses integrate policy evolution, infrastructure development, sectoral restructuring, and regional historical transformation within a unified long-term framework. This gap—particularly concerning the emergence of Southeast Vietnam as a potential marine growth pole in the context of global trade restructuring (OECD, 2016; UNCTAD, 2023)—constitutes the central contribution of the present study.

Methods

This study employs a historical political economy approach that combines quantitative and qualitative analysis to reconstruct the structural transformation of Southeast Vietnam’s marine economy during the period 2007–2025. This approach situates changes in growth performance, sectoral composition, and trade dynamics within broader policy frameworks, spatial planning strategies, and institutional drivers. Rather than merely describing statistical trends, the study seeks to explain the mechanisms underlying the formation and operation of a “marine growth pole” in relation to regional and national development trajectories.

Analytical Methods

First, a time-series analysis is conducted on Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP), sectoral economic structure, and import–export turnover to identify long-term patterns of structural change. Data are organized into three sub-periods—2007–2012, 2013–2019, and 2020–2025—to detect critical structural turning points. Statistical sources include provincial datasets (Ba Ria–Vung Tau Statistical Office, 2016, 2021) and comparative data from Ho Chi Minh City (Hochiminh City Statistical Office, 2017, 2021), enabling regional benchmarking within the Southern Key Economic Region.

Second, a before–after policy comparison is applied around three major milestones: 2007 (the promulgation of the Vietnam Marine Strategy under Resolution No. 09-NQ/TW), 2013 (the acceleration of seaport system planning), and 2020 (the onset of restructuring triggered by the COVID-19 pandemic). These milestones correspond to key policy documents and planning decisions (The Central Committee of the Communist Party of Vietnam, 2007, 2018; Ministry of Transport, 2013, 2017). This comparative

approach allows for assessing the extent to which strategic policy interventions influenced economic growth and sectoral restructuring.

Third, sectoral structure and regional linkage analysis are conducted using a spatial–logistics perspective. According to port regionalization theory, modern ports expand their economic influence through hinterland industrial networks and logistics corridors (Notteboom & Rodrigue, 2005; Rodrigue, 2020). This framework is applied to examine the process of port regionalization and the integration of Southeast Vietnam into East Asian trade and shipping networks. Insights from maritime logistics studies further inform the analysis of port–industry interdependencies (Stopford, 2009; Song & Panayides, 2012).

In addition, a political economy approach is adopted to assess the developmental role of the state in strategic infrastructure investment, spatial planning, and FDI orientation (Linh, 2010; Thom, 2015; Lai, 2022). International development assessments provide additional context for understanding infrastructure-led growth and connectivity strategies (World Bank, 2019; Asian Development Bank, 2022).

Theoretical Framework

The analytical framework integrates three complementary theoretical perspectives. First, growth pole theory provides a lens for interpreting port–industrial clusters as regional growth nuclei capable of generating spillover effects (OECD, 2016). In this perspective, deep-sea ports function not merely as transport infrastructure but as catalysts for industrial concentration and regional integration.

Second, the port-led development model and maritime economics literature (Stopford, 2009; Grammenos, 2010) offer conceptual tools for examining the interconnections between port infrastructure, global trade expansion, and industrialization. UNCTAD’s assessments of maritime transport trends (UNCTAD, 2023) further situate Southeast Vietnam’s transformation within broader shifts in global shipping networks and supply chains.

Third, a maritime political economy approach contextualizes structural transformation within global ocean economy restructuring. International fisheries and sustainability assessments (FAO, 2022) and research on small-scale fisheries transitions (Armitage & Marschke, 2013) help explain the socio-economic implications of shifting from traditional fisheries toward an integrated marine economic structure.

By combining these methodological and theoretical approaches, the study provides a comprehensive assessment of the economic, institutional, and spatial dimensions shaping the emergence of Southeast Vietnam as a marine economic hub.

Results

Activation of the Port–Industrial Structure (2007–2012)

The findings indicate that the period 2007–2012 marked a structural turning point in the formation of Southeast Vietnam’s marine economic hub. This phase can be characterized as the “activation” stage of the port–industrial model, during which the national marine strategy was institutionalized and translated into large-scale infrastructure projects. Resolution No. 09-NQ/TW on the Vietnam Marine Strategy to 2020 (The Central Committee of the Communist Party of Vietnam, 2007) provided the political foundation for prioritizing deep-sea port clusters, heavy industry, and maritime logistics services in the Southern Key Economic Region.

First, investment in deep-sea port infrastructure increased significantly. The Master Plan for the Development of Vietnam’s Seaport System to 2020 (Ministry of Transport, 2013; Lai, 2022), together with subsequent planning adjustments, established the strategic role of the Southeast Seaport Cluster—particularly the Cai Mep–Thi Vai deep-sea port complex. During this period, the capacity to accommodate large vessels expanded, gradually enabling direct connections to trans-Pacific and European shipping routes and reducing reliance on regional transshipment hubs (UNCTAD, 2019).

From the perspective of port regionalization theory, this transition signified a shift from a locally oriented port to one performing regional and international gateway functions, triggering the restructuring of its economic hinterland (Notteboom & Rodrigue, 2005; Rodrigue, 2020).

The expansion of port infrastructure was accompanied by coordinated investment in coastal industrial zones and transport connectivity. Reports from the Ba Ria–Vung Tau Management Board of Industrial Zones (2013) show rapid increases in industrial land area and occupancy rates during this period, reflecting industrial agglomeration linked to port development. From a growth pole perspective, the port–industrial cluster emerged as a new regional growth nucleus capable of generating spillover effects into supporting industries and services (OECD, 2016).

Second, foreign direct investment (FDI) in heavy industry and petrochemicals increased markedly. Provincial data indicate a substantial inflow of FDI into steel production, petrochemicals, gas-fired power generation, and large-scale processing industries between 2007 and 2012 (Ba Ria–Vung Tau Management Board of Industrial Zones, 2013; Lai, 2022). The establishment of heavy industrial projects along the coast not only altered the regional value-added structure but also repositioned Southeast Vietnam within regional supply chains. Maritime economics literature underscores that deep-sea port infrastructure constitutes a necessary condition for attracting large-scale industrial projects by providing logistics advantages and direct import–export capabilities (Stopford, 2009; Grammenos, 2010).

The broader context of post-WTO trade globalization and expanding Asian supply chains further facilitated capital and production relocation into Vietnam (World Bank, 2019). From a political economy perspective, the state’s developmental role—through spatial planning, public investment, and FDI incentives—was instrumental in shaping this trajectory (Thom, 2015; Lai, 2022). The coordination between central authorities and provincial governments effectively created a “development coalition” centered on port infrastructure and heavy industry.

Third, the share of agriculture and fisheries declined noticeably within the regional economic structure. Time-series analysis of GRDP reveals a gradual reduction in the proportion of agriculture, forestry, and fisheries in Ba Ria–Vung Tau Province between 2007 and 2012, as industry and services expanded (Ba Ria–Vung Tau Statistical Office, 2016). This shift reflects a transition from resource-based livelihoods toward an industrial–logistics production model. At the social level, however, this transformation generated challenges for traditional fishing communities, which faced dual pressures from declining marine resources and increasing competition over coastal space (Armitage & Marschke, 2013; FAO, 2014).

Overall, the 2007–2012 period can be interpreted as a phase of “infrastructure and institutional accumulation” underpinning a port-led development model. The convergence of the national marine strategy (The Central Committee of the Communist Party of Vietnam, 2007), port system planning (Ministry of Transport, 2013), and industrial FDI flows established the foundation for a new economic structure. Although full integration into global trade networks had not yet been achieved, the structural transformations during this period clearly delineated the trajectory from traditional fisheries toward an industrialized and globally oriented marine growth pole (Lai, 2022).

Expansion and Deep Integration (2013–2019)

If the period 2007–2012 laid the infrastructural and institutional foundations for the port–industrial structure, the years 2013–2019 marked a phase of scale expansion and deeper integration into global trade networks. Three defining features characterize this stage: (i) deep-sea ports receiving mother vessels operating direct routes to the United States and the European Union; (ii) rapid growth of logistics services and supporting industries; and (iii) GRDP per capita exceeding the national average.

First, deep-sea ports formally entered transoceanic shipping networks. The revision and consolidation of the Southeast Seaport Cluster master plan (Ministry of Transport, 2017) provided the legal and strategic framework for expanding capacity and upgrading infrastructure to accommodate large container vessels. From the mid-2010s onward, the Cai Mep–Thi Vai port complex began handling mother vessels exceeding 100,000 DWT, operating direct services to the United States and Europe and reducing reliance

on transshipment hubs such as Singapore or Hong Kong (UNCTAD, 2019). According to port regionalization theory, once a port acquires the capacity to receive mother vessels and establish long-haul direct routes, its role shifts from a national gateway to a strategic node within global supply chains (Notteboom & Rodrigue, 2005; Rodrigue, 2020).

At the strategic level, Resolution No. 36-NQ/TW on the Sustainable Development Strategy for Vietnam's Marine Economy to 2030 (The Central Committee of the Communist Party of Vietnam, 2018) reaffirmed the central position of the southern deep-sea port cluster within the national marine economic structure. This shift reflects a transition from "infrastructure activation" to "integration optimization," in which port infrastructure is no longer merely a technical asset but a strategic instrument for spatial-economic restructuring.

Second, logistics services and supporting industries expanded rapidly. As the port complex achieved large-scale operations and direct US–EU connectivity, demand surged for warehousing, multimodal transport, supply-chain management, and industrial support services. Reports from the Ba Ria–Vung Tau Management Board of Industrial Zones (2018, 2020) indicate steadily rising occupancy rates in industrial parks, with a growing concentration of FDI projects in manufacturing and logistics services. This trajectory aligns with the port-led development model, whereby seaports function as anchor points for industrial value chains and service clusters (Stopford, 2009; Grammenos, 2010; Song & Panayides, 2012).

The broader global context during 2013–2019 was marked by supply-chain reconfiguration across Asia, particularly in electronics, mechanical engineering, and petrochemicals. According to the World Bank (2019), improvements in logistics performance and port capacity were critical to enhancing Vietnam's export competitiveness. Southeast Vietnam, benefiting from deep-sea port advantages and an extensive network of industrial zones, leveraged these trends to expand outward-oriented production.

From a political economy perspective, the state continued to play a coordinating role through integrated port–industry–transport planning and investment climate reforms (Thom, 2015; Linh, 2010). The coordination between central and provincial authorities reinforced the region's position as an industrial–logistics hub closely linked to international trade.

Third, GRDP per capita surpassed the national average. Statistical analysis indicates that between 2013 and 2019, GRDP per capita in Ba Ria–Vung Tau Province consistently remained significantly higher than the national average (Ba Ria–Vung Tau Statistical Office, 2016, 2021). This reflects the spillover effects of industrial and port-service expansion on local income levels. Growth pole theory suggests that once a growth nucleus reaches sufficient scale, it generates not only direct value-added but also stimulates auxiliary industries and social services (OECD, 2016).

Nevertheless, deeper integration also generated new vulnerabilities. Dependence on global trade flows, environmental pressures on coastal ecosystems, and labor restructuring emerged as pressing concerns. UNCTAD (2023) notes that volatility in global trade and supply-chain disruptions can significantly affect major regional hub ports. At the same time, expanding coastal industrialization necessitates sustainable governance to mitigate spatial conflicts with traditional livelihoods and marine resource use (FAO, 2022).

Overall, the 2013–2019 period represents a shift from "infrastructure formation" to "global network integration." The Southeast deep-sea port cluster evolved from a national infrastructure project into a critical link in transoceanic transport chains. Logistics services and supporting industries expanded rapidly, contributing to rising per capita income and local economic restructuring. During this phase, Southeast Vietnam moved closer to becoming a deeply integrated marine growth pole, albeit one increasingly exposed to the structural vulnerabilities of a globalized ocean economy.

Crisis and Restructuring (2020–2025)

The period 2020–2025 unfolded amid the unprecedented global crisis triggered by the COVID-19 pandemic, generating severe disruptions to international trade and supply chains. For Southeast Vietnam—an outward-oriented port and industrial hub—this phase represented both a period of substantial

disruption and an opportunity for structural adjustment and strategic repositioning within regional trade networks.

First, COVID-19 significantly affected supply chains and maritime transport. UNCTAD (2020, 2023) reports indicate that the pandemic disrupted cargo flows, caused port congestion, container shortages, and unprecedented spikes in freight rates. Vietnam in general, and the Southeast deep-sea port cluster in particular, faced supply interruptions in raw materials and export markets. Nevertheless, owing to prior investments in deep-sea port infrastructure (Ministry of Transport, 2017), the Cai Mep–Thi Vai complex maintained its critical role in international container shipping and even recorded output growth in certain peak years amid global supply-chain restructuring (UNCTAD, 2023).

Time-series analysis of GRDP and trade turnover for 2020–2022 shows short-term stagnation followed by relatively rapid recovery, supported by industrial export advantages and the region’s embeddedness in regional supply chains (Ba Ria–Vung Tau Statistical Office, 2021). According to the World Bank (2022), Vietnam ranked among the fastest trade-recovering economies post-pandemic, attributable to effective public health control and sustained industrial production. This reinforced Southeast Vietnam’s role as a key node in Asia-Pacific value chains.

Second, the region underwent strategic repositioning within regional trade networks. The pandemic and geopolitical tensions accelerated supply-chain diversification (“China+1”), creating opportunities for port–industrial centers with reliable infrastructure and stable investment environments. Within the port regionalization framework, competitiveness increasingly depends not only on port capacity but also on hinterland logistics integration and multimodal connectivity (Rodrigue, 2020). Benefiting from an extensive industrial park system and strong transport links to Ho Chi Minh City and the Southern Key Economic Region, Southeast Vietnam progressively consolidated its role as a regional distribution and transshipment hub.

Resolution No. 36-NQ/TW on sustainable marine economic development (The Central Committee of the Communist Party of Vietnam, 2018) continued to guide restructuring toward greater efficiency and sustainability. At the provincial level, logistics development strategies and port digitalization initiatives were intensified to enhance competitiveness (Ba Ria–Vung Tau Industrial Zones Authority, 2020). As OECD (2016) argues, growth poles sustain their spillover capacity only through continuous adaptation to global volatility and institutional upgrading.

Third, the period witnessed a transition toward energy transformation and the blue economy. A defining feature of 2020–2025 has been the gradual shift from traditional heavy industry toward energy and sustainable marine sectors. In the context of decarbonization commitments and energy transition, Southeast Vietnam has emerged as a hub for gas-fired power, LNG infrastructure, and offshore wind potential. FAO (2022) and UNCTAD (2023) emphasize the importance of a sustainable blue economy in the post-COVID era, integrating economic expansion with marine ecosystem protection.

From a maritime political economy perspective, this shift reflects a broader transformation in the structure of marine economic power: from resource extraction and heavy industry toward integrated models combining clean energy, advanced logistics, and maritime technologies (Stopford, 2009). The state continues to play a coordinating role through marine spatial planning, investment orientation, and renewable energy regulatory frameworks (The Central Committee of the Communist Party of Vietnam, 2018).

Overall, 2020–2025 represents not merely a period of crisis but one of strategic restructuring. Southeast Vietnam has navigated the global supply-chain shock while repositioning itself as an integrated marine economic hub—where deep-sea ports, manufacturing industries, modern logistics, and emerging marine energy sectors converge. The shift toward a blue economy signals an evolution from an “industrial growth pole” to an “integrated and sustainable growth pole,” opening a new developmental phase in the region’s maritime economic history.

Discussion

The findings indicate that the marine economic growth model of Southeast Vietnam during 2007–2025 exhibits three defining characteristics: (i) the state as a strategic infrastructure builder; (ii) strong dependence on global trade; and (iii) limited domestic value-added in several key sectors. These characteristics raise a fundamental theoretical question: has the region genuinely evolved into an endogenous “growth pole” in the Perrouxian sense, or does it function primarily as a strategic node within East Asian supply chains?

First, the state’s developmental role constitutes a structural foundation of the model. Beginning with Resolution No. 09-NQ/TW (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2007) and reinforced by Resolution No. 36-NQ/TW (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2018), Vietnam’s marine strategy has been institutionalized as a long-term national development orientation. Master plans for the national seaport system and the Southeast seaport cluster (Ministry of Transport, 2013, 2017) demonstrate concentrated and strategic investment in deep-sea port infrastructure. Within growth pole theory, key infrastructure and public investment serve as catalytic mechanisms that stimulate capital accumulation and spatial concentration (OECD, 2016). The Southeast case suggests that the state has acted not merely as regulator but as an architect of economic space, shaping the region’s position within global trade networks.

However, this characteristic also reflects significant dependence on policy decisions and public investment. When port infrastructure and industrial zones form the backbone of growth, questions arise regarding the region’s endogenous innovation capacity and structural flexibility. From a political economy perspective, sustainable growth poles require an effective institutional framework, a dynamic domestic private sector, and strong interregional linkages (Thom, 2015; Lai, 2022).

Second, growth remains highly dependent on global trade and supply chains. The integration of Cai Mep–Thi Vai into direct trans-Pacific and Europe-bound shipping routes (UNCTAD, 2019, 2023) has positioned Southeast Vietnam at the core of regional logistics networks. As Notteboom and Rodrigue (2005) argue, when a port becomes a node in global transport systems, it benefits from cargo flows but simultaneously becomes vulnerable to trade volatility. The COVID-19 pandemic illustrated the structural fragility of port-centered economies heavily reliant on global trade (UNCTAD, 2020).

Such dependence situates Southeast Vietnam more as a strategic node than as a controlling center of value chains. According to the World Bank (2019), upgrading within global supply chains requires not only logistics infrastructure but also domestic technological capabilities and supporting industries. If most value-added activities remain concentrated in transportation, assembly, or processing, the region’s role may remain circumscribed within East Asia’s division of labor.

Third, domestic value-added remains constrained in several sectors. Although GRDP per capita exceeds the national average (Ba Ria–Vung Tau Statistical Office, 2021), the value-added structure reveals a large share in capital-intensive manufacturing and energy sectors heavily dependent on foreign direct investment. Stopford (2009) notes that within port-led development models, the absence of robust supporting industries and domestic technological upgrading limits spillover effects. This pattern is particularly evident in petrochemicals, steel, and logistics, where technology and value chains are largely dominated by foreign enterprises.

These three characteristics prompt a reconsideration of the theoretical classification of Southeast Vietnam. Has it become a “growth pole” in the Perrouxian sense—characterized by strong spillover dynamics and endogenous momentum—or does it function primarily as an integrated node within East Asia’s production network? OECD (2016) suggests that a genuine growth pole must foster technological innovation, knowledge accumulation, and enhanced domestic competitiveness. While Southeast Vietnam demonstrates success in scale and integration, technological spillovers and domestic enterprise linkages remain areas requiring further consolidation.

Long-term sustainability further emerges as a central concern. Geopolitical volatility, trade conflicts, and supply-chain restructuring pose risks to export-dependent hubs (UNCTAD, 2023). Simultaneously, green

transition and sustainable marine development demand structural adjustments toward lower emissions and ecosystem protection (FAO, 2022). Resolution No. 36-NQ/TW (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2018) emphasizes sustainable marine economic development; however, balancing heavy industry, logistics expansion, and marine environmental conservation remains a complex long-term challenge.

In sum, Southeast Vietnam has approached the status of an integrated marine growth pole in terms of infrastructure and trade scale. Yet its current character embodies both attributes of a “growth pole” and those of a strategic node within East Asian supply chains. The region’s future trajectory will depend on its capacity to upgrade domestic value-added, deepen regional linkages, and adapt to green transition imperatives amid an increasingly volatile geopolitical landscape.

Conclusion

This study has examined the formation and transformation of Southeast Vietnam’s marine economic center during 2007–2025 as a representative case of the port–industrial development model under globalization. From a foundation rooted in fisheries and traditional resource extraction, the region has evolved into an integrated economic space combining deep-sea ports, heavy industry, logistics, and marine energy, with deep insertion into international trade networks.

The three developmental phases reveal a relatively coherent trajectory. The period 2007–2012 constituted the activation phase of the port–industrial structure, characterized by strategic infrastructure investment and large-scale FDI inflows. The years 2013–2019 marked expansion and deep integration, as deep-sea ports entered transoceanic shipping routes and logistics services expanded rapidly, contributing to GRDP per capita surpassing the national average. During 2020–2025, despite the profound disruptions caused by the pandemic and geopolitical volatility, the region maintained its central role through supply-chain adaptability and a strategic shift toward energy transition and the blue economy.

Nevertheless, structural constraints remain evident. The growth model continues to rely heavily on global trade and foreign direct investment, while domestic value-added and indigenous technological capacity require further strengthening. Southeast Vietnam thus embodies a dual character: it approximates a “growth pole” in terms of infrastructural concentration and economic scale, yet simultaneously functions as a strategic node within East Asian supply chains. This duality underscores the need to upgrade its position in global value chains, deepen domestic enterprise linkages, and foster high-technology supporting industries.

In the long term, the sustainability of Southeast Vietnam’s marine economic center will depend on three interrelated factors: (i) resilience and adaptability to geopolitical and trade volatility; (ii) green transition and sustainable marine spatial governance; and (iii) enhancement of endogenous innovation and knowledge accumulation. If these challenges are effectively addressed, Southeast Vietnam may transcend its role as a logistics gateway and emerge as an integrated marine economic hub with substantive spillover effects at both regional and national levels amid the ongoing restructuring of the global economy.

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